

Synthesis, spectroscopic characterization with computational modeling and epoxidation activity of two iron(III)-Schiff base complexes

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Two non-heme mononuclear iron(III) complexes, [Fe(L)Cl] (1) and [Fe(L)Br] (2) containing a (N,O)-donor Schiff base ligand, (H₂L = 2-((5-((2-hydroxyphenylimino)methyl)furan-2-yl)methyleneamino)phenol), have been synthesized and isolated in pure state. The structural formulation for iron complexes have been determined by different physico-chemical methods. Room temperature magnetic measurement for both 1 and 2 indicates the existence of high spin iron(III) species in their solid state. The structural consolidation for the iron complexes (1 and 2) has been performed through theoretical modeling with B3LYP density functional theory (DFT) using 6-31g(d) basis set. The optimized structures agree very well with the experimental proposed structures. The iron(III)-Schiff base complexes have been evaluated as effective catalytic systems towards alkene epoxidation using (*E*)-stilbene as a convenient in presence of *tert*-butylhydrogenperoxide (TBHP). It is revealed that 2 has better catalytic efficacy than 1 in terms of the yield of the reaction for both the iron complexes.

Keywords: Iron(III), Schiff base, spectroscopic methods, epoxidation activity, DFT study.

Introduction

Transition metal complexes containing oxygen and nitrogen based polydentate ligands are of great interest for having their diverse geometric configurations, structural lability, and electronic reactivity¹⁻³. Iron is the most prevalent transition metal in nature. Among the transition metal complexes, iron complexes have significant contribution in developing utility materials of industrial and biological significance⁴⁻⁶. Synthetic ligands have an influencing effect on the design of metal catalysts in order to bring high order of reactivity and selectivity for different organic transformations. Sterically and electronically tuned ligands in association with iron metal ions may therefore result in development of efficient and low cost catalysts for enantioselective synthesis⁷. Further efforts in tuning iron catalysts concerning handling, stability, activity and selectivity have to be made to bring the catalytic systems closer to large scale industrial

application. Thus, finding of effective catalytic systems that use clean, inexpensive terminal oxidants, such as molecular oxygen or hydrogen peroxide, are highly desired from both environmental and economic point of views.

Epoxidation of olefins and arenes^{8,9} is a marvelous transformation in synthetic organic chemistry⁸ since the epoxy compounds are widely used in the preparation of wide range of commodity chemicals¹⁰. In relation to epoxidation, hydrogen peroxide is treated possibly the best terminal oxidant after molecular oxygen from environmental and industrial perspective^{10,11}. Among the transition metal complexes, iron, cobalt and manganese-Schiff base complexes have drawn special interest for their significant contribution in catalytic epoxidation reactions^{10,12a,b}. But the real breakthrough in transition-metal catalyzed asymmetric epoxidation of unfunctionalized alkenes was made in 1990 when two research groups, Jacobsen

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et al. and Katsuki *et al.*, independently reported the use of optically active Mn^{III}-salen complexes as epoxidation catalysts¹³. Cobalt complexes have also a striking effect in the transformation of olefin to its epoxide product under normal chemical ambience¹⁴. Few number of iron-Schiff base complexes are available which have been involved in this purpose. Among the iron complexes, Fe^{III}(salen)/(porphyrins)¹⁵⁻¹⁷ have already been paid special attention as effective catalysts towards epoxidation of olefins. However, several issues are still unresolved, in particular the greener approach of the reactions, nature of the oxidants, turnover number and the selectivity of the products. So the search for new epoxidation catalyst is one of the most important topics connected with both industrial and academic research. With an aim to develop more active catalytic systems towards epoxidation reactions we have synthesized and spectroscopically characterized two new mononuclear iron(III) complexes containing a (N,O)-donor Schiff base ligand. Both the complexes exhibit good epoxidation activity towards (*E*)-stilbene in acetonitrile using *tert*-butylhydrogenperoxide (TBHP) as an oxidant under normal condition. It is revealed that iron(III) complex **2** has better catalytic efficacy than **1** in terms of the yield of epoxidation reaction.

Results and discussion

Synthesis, spectroscopic characterization and solution properties of the iron(III) complexes:

The complexes **1** and **2** were prepared by mixing of ferric halide salts with Schiff base ligand in 1:1 molar ratio in methanol and DCM solvent mixture (Scheme 1). The iron(III) complexes have been isolated as a dark violet coloured compound. Based on elemental analysis and other fundamental spectro-

Scheme 1. Synthetic route for the iron(III)-Schiff base complexes.

scopic techniques the complexes were formulated as [Fe(L)X] (X = Cl⁻, Br⁻). Room temperature magnetic measurement indicates the presence of +3 oxidation state of the iron centres in **1** and **2** as reveal from $\mu_{\text{eff}} = 5.87$ and 5.81 BM respectively. The complexes were soluble in common organic solvents such as MeOH, MeCN etc.

The IR spectra of the iron(III)-Schiff base complexes have been characterized mainly by the presence of strong peaks at 1627 and 1638 cm⁻¹ which are attributed to the stretching frequencies of coordinated C=N (imine) group. Further, IR spectra exhibit the characteristic peaks for coordinated phenolate-O at 1307 and 1311 cm⁻¹ for both the complexes respectively (Figs. S1 and S2). Other characteristic bands in the range 500 – 900 cm⁻¹ may be assigned to M-X, M-N and M-O stretching modes¹⁸.

The UV-Vis absorption spectrum of the free ligand showed prominent bands at 267 and 349 nm respectively, assigned to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ and $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions in the aromatic ring and the imine chromophore of the ligand¹⁹. Upon complex formation, those transitions still appeared in the spectra of the complexes, but $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ is shifted towards longer wavelength, confirming the coordination via the lone pairs of electron of the nitrogen atoms of the Schiff base to the metal ion (C=N \rightarrow Mⁿ⁺ ion) (Fig. S3). The UV-Vis spectral data for both the iron complexes in acetonitrile medium shows metal based broad transition in the visible region. The existence of low energy bands at 521 and 513 nm (Fig. S3) for **1** and **2** respectively in the visible region further confirmed the coordination of imine nitrogen and phenolate oxygen with Fe^{III} ion¹⁹.

In order to probe the solution stability of iron(III) complexes we have recorded UV-Vis spectra and molar conductance for **1** and **2** in acetonitrile solution at room temperature. Low intensity and broad transition at ~ 521 nm and ~ 513 nm for **1** and **2** remained almost unaffected over a period of at least 3 days revealing that the complexes are quite stable in solution at room temperature. This stability of the complexes in solution is further consolidated from the ESI-mass spectrometry. The mass spectra for **1**

and **2** in acetonitrile medium (Figs. S4 and S5) are in good agreement with the theoretical molecular mass of the complexes and also confirmed mononuclear nature of the iron(III) complexes. The ESI-mass spectra (Figs. S4 and S5) of **1** and **2** show molecular ion peaks at m/z 396.35 and 441.29 respectively. We have also recorded molar conductivity measurements for the two monoiron(III)-Schiff base complexes at room temperature. The molar conductance values in 10^{-4} (M) dry acetonitrile solution for the two complexes are 111 and 117 $\text{m}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$ and support in favour of 1:1 type electrolyte in solution. The iron(III) complexes in acetonitrile solution releases terminal halide ions from the primary zone of coordination and acts as $[\text{Fe}(\text{L})(\text{solvent})]^+ : \text{X}^-$ electrolyte.

Molecular modeling analysis with structural description:

Though we have isolated the compound in pure state but remain unsuccessful to produce single crystals instead of repeated attempts in different solvent mixture and reaction conditions. For this reason, we have used TD-DFT at molecular level with the help of computational molecular modeling. Molecular modeling has been successfully used to detect three dimensional arrangements of atoms in complexes by means of semi-empirical molecular orbital calculations at the B3LYP level using 6-31G(d,p) basis set provided by the Gaussian 09 suite. Their utilization in the demonstration of molecular structure and structural properties data of the iron(III) complexes conducted with calculated HOMO and LUMO energies. Selected bond lengths and bond angles of the iron complexes are presented in Table 1. The optimized structures of the hexa-coordinated iron(III) complexes are shown in Figs. 1 and 2. In the gas phase, (O,N)-donor Schiff base ligand (H_2L) exhibits its pentadentate behaviour towards Fe^{III} centre and forms an octahedral structure in combination with a terminal halide ion. Molar conductivity measurements for the two iron complexes in methanolic solution indicates their 1:1 electrolytic nature and accounts for the incorporation of halide ion at the primary zone of coordination for iron centres. The structure of iron(III) complexes seem to be a distorted octahedral geometry in gas phase. The important geometric pa-

Table 1. Important bond distance and bond angle parameters for iron(III) complex **1**

Bond	Distance (Å)	Bond	Distance (Å)
Fe1-N2	1.946	Fe1-O14	2.042
Fe1-O19	1.918	Fe1-N37	1.983
Fe1-O38	2.017	Fe1-Cl39	2.354
Bond angle (°)		Bond angle (°)	
N37-Fe1-N2	157.852	N37-Fe1-O19	79.594
N37-Fe1-O38	81.304	O19-Fe1-O14	160.387
O19-Fe1-O38	97.256	O19-Fe1-N2	78.976
Cl39-Fe1-O38	167.021	Cl39-Fe1-O14	88.056
Cl39-Fe1-N2	92.517	O19-Fe1-Cl39	78.976

Fig. 1. Optimized structure of the iron(III) complex (**1**).

Fig. 2. Optimized structure of the iron(III) complex (**2**).

Parameters of the iron(III) complexes are presented in Table 1 and details geometric parameters of the iron(III) complexes are presented in Tables S1 and S2. The iron(III)-ligand bond lengths vary from 1.91 to 2.35 Å for **1** and 1.91 to 2.55 Å for **2**. The maximum bond lengths in **1** and **2** are found to be 2.35 Å and 2.55 Å for Fe1-Cl39 and Fe1-Br39 respectively. The maximum bond angles in **1** and **2** are found to be 167.021° and 161.798° for <O38-Fe1-C139 and <O38-Fe1-Br39 as respectively, while the minimum bond angles are found to be 78.9° and 79.5° for <O19-Fe1-N2 and <O19-Fe1-N37 in **1** and **2** respectively. The difference between HOMO and LUMO is a measure of the reactivity of a compound. According to the electronic behavior, HOMO acts as electron donor and LUMO acts as electron acceptor. The calculated energy gap between HOMO and LUMO in **1** and **2** are 178.83 and 179.10 kcal/mol respectively (Figs. 3 and 4). Computational calculations on the energy of different molecular orbitals always helpful to depict the chemical activity for molecules²⁰. Prediction of energy differences between frontier molecular orbitals through theoretical calculation is also remain a fundamental step before investigation of molecular properties like catalysis, optical properties etc.²¹. In this case, computational

Fig. 3. Frontier molecular orbital's contribution in the ground state of iron(III)-Schiff base (**1**).

Fig. 4. Frontier molecular orbital's contribution in the ground state of iron(III)-Schiff base (**2**).

study reveals that energy differences between frontier orbitals (HOMO and LUMO) are moderate for both the complexes and recommends their higher chemical reactivity in epoxidation.

Epoxidation of alkenes catalyzed by the iron-Schiff base complexes and mechanistic inference:

The iron(III) catalysts were tested for epoxidation of alkenes using (*E*)-stilbene as a model substrate. The iron catalysed epoxidation reactions (Scheme 2) are carried out at room temperature with both **1** and **2** in the presence of TBHP in acetonitrile. We have also performed controlled experiments under identical reaction conditions without addition of iron(III)-Schiff base catalysts (blank experiments). No epoxide formation was traced out under such reaction condition for 2 h time interval. The amount of epoxides was recorded in isolated yield for (*E*)-stilbene and characterized by ¹H NMR (Fig. S6). The yield of epoxides in optimized conditions for **1** and **2** were

Scheme 2. Iron(III) complex catalysed epoxidation routes.

Table 2. Important bond distance and bond angle parameters for iron(III) complex **2**

Bond	Distance (Å)	Bond	Distance (Å)
Fe1-N2	1.943	Fe1-O14	2.045
Fe1-O19	1.917	Fe1-N37	1.983
Fe1-O38	2.025	Fe1-Br39	2.551
Bond angle (°)		Bond angle (°)	
N37-Fe1-N2	157.697	N37-Fe1-O19	79.505
N37-Fe1-O38	81.207	O19-Fe1-O14	159.878
O14-Fe1-O38	82.995	O14-Fe1-N2	81.173
O14-Fe1-N37	97.021	Br39-Fe1-O14	87.922
Br39-Fe1-N2	92.732	O38-Fe1-Br39	161.798

found as 87% and 83% with TBHP.

We have also investigated the optimization effect of the catalyst. To optimize the amount of catalyst, concentration of the catalysts were varied between 3 to 6 mg per 0.2 mmol of alkenes. Increase in the yield of epoxides were observed for both **1** and **2** when the amount of catalysts we increased from 3 to 5 mg but very little amount of yield was increased with further increment of catalyst amount up to 6 mg which is negligible. Thus in presence of ~5 mg of each of the catalysts, the epoxidation reactions were studied in varying amounts of TBHP with an aim to determine the optimized effect of oxidants. The yield of the epoxides was also significantly increased with increasing the concentration of the oxidant, TBHP. The catalytic reactions were also examined with varying time period between 1.5 h, 2.5 h and 3 h where we observed the epoxide yield attained the peak after 2.5 h of reaction and remained the same even after 3 h. An optimum of ~5 mg of catalyst (for both **1** and **2**), 70% TBHP (42 mg, 0.5 mmol) (per 0.2 mmol of the substrate) and 2.5 h reaction time are ideal for achieving the best yield.

We have reviewed extensive scientific literatures to draw mechanistic inferences for these epoxidation reactions²². It is commonly observed that metallo-porphyrins and metallo-salens show similar electronic properties and catalytic activity²³. Here, our synthesized iron(III)-Schiff base complexes belong to metallo-salen class of compound. The epoxidation of alkenes catalyzed by iron, cobalt and manganese complexes

is generally believed to proceed through oxo-metallic species of higher oxidation states like oxo-iron(V) intermediates participating in cytochrome P450-mediated oxidations²⁴. Actually, porphyrin- and salen-based transition metal complexes react with oxidants, such as iodosylarenes, sodium hypochlorite, and hydrogen peroxide, which are able to donate one oxygen atom (single oxygen atom donors) to form an oxo-metal species, which then relays the oxygen to the substrate. The concept of this widely accepted oxygen-rebound mechanism was introduced by Groves *et al.*²⁵, and is outlined in Scheme 3. Oxo transfer from metals to alkenes results in a net two-electron reduction of the metal complex (Scheme 3). Therefore, only metals, such as Fe^{III}, Mn^{III}, Cr^{III} and Ru(III), that are capable of shuttling between oxidation states are effective in oxo-transfer catalysis. Previously, it was observed that iron-porphyrin complexes catalyze olefin epoxidation through a high valent Fe^{IV}-porphyrin species, [FeO(P[•])]⁺ which was well detected by spectral techniques *in situ*²⁶.

Scheme 3. Transition metal-catalyzed epoxidation of alkenes by oxygen rebound. LM = transition metal complex (L = porphyrin or salen), XO = oxygen atom donor (e.g. PhIO, NaOCl, O₂/reductant, H₂O₂).

In our case, addition of TBHP to Fe^{III}-Schiff base complexes turned reddish to intense violet coloured solution, which faded rapidly upon addition of *trans*-stilbene substrate. We have studied optical changes for these iron complexes during the course of epoxidation reactions. Both the complexes have a broad peak at ~516 nm with the appearance of one high intensity peak at ~277 nm. Upon addition of TBHP to iron(III) complexes, after 1 h the optical spectra displayed one new shoulder at ~479 nm with disappearance of the band at 516 nm. All the observations suggested the formation of a higher valent

Table 3. Catalytic epoxidation of (*E*)-stilbene in acetonitrile by TBHP using **1** and **2** as the catalysts under different conditions

Entry	Catalyst (mg)		TBHP (mg)	Yield (%) ^a CH ₃ CN	
	1	2		1	2
1	3	3	42	72	77
2	4	4	42	78	83
3	5	5	42	83	87
4	6	6	42	85	88
5	3	3	–	53	56
6	4	4	–	63	65
7	5	5	–	71	75
8	6	6	–	73	78
9	5	5	30	63	67
10	5	5	60	88	90
11	5	5	–	54	55
12	5	5	–	75	80

^aIsolated yield of epoxide.

Fe(oxo) after addition of TBHP, that was consistent with earlier study by D. Das and group²⁷. After 1 day, the spectra didn't match either the original spectra or the spectra after 1 h of addition of TBHP. Probably, after 24 h, the catalysts lost their activity. So, from these spectrophotometric observations, it can be proposed that the iron(III)-Schiff base complexes in presence of TBHP are able to promote the Fe^{III} to their higher valent iron-oxo species, which transforms substrate to its epoxide product in the course of reactions.

Conclusions

We have synthesized and spectroscopically characterized two new iron(III)-Schiff base complexes (**1** and **2**). Computation modeling in gas phase on the molecular structures with B3LYP density functional theory (DFT) using 6-31g(d) basis set helps us to consolidate the structural formulation. Room temperature magnetic measurement for both **1** and **2** indicates the existence of high spin iron(III) species in their solid state. The catalytic efficacy of **1** and **2** have been investigated as epoxidation catalysts towards (*E*)-stilbene as convenient substrate in presence of terminal oxidant, TBHP in CH₃CN. Between the two iron(III) complexes, **2** has better catalytic

efficacy for having better leaving group (Br) compared to **1**. Optical changes are observed during addition of oxidant (TBHP) and substrate (*E*-stilbene) which strongly recommends that epoxidation are proceed via higher valent iron-oxo species in the course of epoxidation.

Experimental

Materials and methods:

High purity furan-2,5-dicarboxaldehyde (Sigma, Germany), 2-aminophenol (Merck, India), iron(III) chloride (Merck, India), and iron(III)bromide (Aldrich, USA), all other solvents were purchased from the respective concerns and used as received. (*E*)-Stilbene was obtained from Sigma-Aldrich Corporation (St. Louis, MO, USA). All other chemicals and solvents were of analytical grade and were used as received without further purification.

Physical measurements:

Elemental analyses (carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen) were performed on a Perkin-Elmer 2400 CHNS/O elemental analyzer. Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectra (KBr discs, 4000–300 cm⁻¹) were recorded using a FTIR-8400S Shimadzu spectrophotometer in the range 400–3600 cm⁻¹. Ground-state absorption measurements were made with a Jasco model V-730 UV-Vis spectrophotometer. The ¹H nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectra were recorded on a Bruker DPX-500 MHz spectrometer. Electrospray ionization (EI) mass spectrum was recorded using a Q-tof-micro quadrupole mass spectrometer. Molar conductivities were recorded using a Metler conductivity meter. A Gouy balance was used to determine the magnetic moments of the powdered samples, employing Hg^{II} tetrathiocyanatocobaltate(II) as a calibrant. Diamagnetic corrections were made from the Pascal's constants.

Preparation of H₂L and iron(III) complexes (**1** and **2**):

The Schiff base ligand was synthesized following a reported procedure¹⁷. 2-Aminophenol (0.218 g, 2 mmol) was refluxed with furan-2,5-dicarbaldehyde (0.124 g, 1 mmol) in 50 mL dehydrated alcohol. After 6 h the reaction solution was kept in open

atmosphere and yellowish orange coloured crystalline compound was separated out from solution, which was dried and stored *in vacuo* over CaCl_2 for subsequent use.

Yield of H_2L : ~ 0.283 g ($\sim 92\%$). Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3$ (H_2L): C, 70.58; H, 4.61; N, 9.15. Found: C, 70.55; H, 4.57; N, 9.13; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}): 1613, 1589 ($\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$), 3550–3350 ($\nu_{\text{Ph-OH}}$), 1297, 1243 (ν_{PhO}); UV-Vis (λ_{max} , nm, 10^{-4} M MeCN): 267, 349.

A methanolic solution (5 mL) of H_2L (0.306 g, 1 mmol) was added dropwise to a solution of FeCl_3 (0.162 g, 1 mmol) and FeBr_3 (0.295 g, 1 mmol) in the dichloromethane solvent (10 mL). The colour of the solutions turned instantly dark violet and the solution were stirred for 3 h on a magnetic stirrer. The violet solutions were kept in air for slow evaporation to obtain pure products.

Yield of **1**: ~ 0.117 g ($\sim 69\%$ based on metal salt). Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3\text{ClFe}$ (**1**): C, 54.65; H, 3.06; N, 7.08. Found: C, 54.60; H, 3.01; N, 7.13; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}): 1627, 1598 ($\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$), 1307, 1249, 1211 (ν_{PhO}); UV-Vis (λ_{max} , nm, 10^{-4} M MeCN): 283, 521; [$1+\text{H}^+$] m/z 396.35.

Yield of **2**: ~ 0.209 g ($\sim 71\%$ based on metal salt). Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3\text{BrFe}$ (**2**): C, 49.13; H, 2.75; N, 6.37. Found: C, 49.10; H, 2.69; N, 6.41; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}): 1638, 1607 ($\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$), 1311, 1255, 1221 (ν_{PhO}); UV-Vis (λ_{max} , nm, 10^{-4} M MeCN): 287, 513; [$2+\text{H}^+$] m/z 441.29.

Computational details:

All the electronic structures calculations were carried out using the Gaussian 09 programme suite. Without symmetrical constrains, all geometries for ground states (S_0) were optimized with gradient-corrected exchange functional B3LYP and [6-31g(d)] basis set²⁸. All minimized geometries were checked by frequency calculations to be true minima. A widely used gradient corrected correlated functional is the LYP functional of Lee, Yang and Parr. A popular gradient-corrected exchange functional is one proposed by Becke in 1988. The combination of the two forms the B-LYP method. The best known of these hybrids functional is Becke's three-parameter for-

mulation; B3LYP model is used as it is a hybrid model with corrections for both gradient and exchange correlations.

General method for the epoxidation of alkene:

Catalyst (0.01 mmol) and alkene (0.2 mmol) were dissolved in 10 mL acetonitrile. 70% TBHP (42 mg, 0.5 mmol) was added portion wise to this solution followed by stirring at room temperature for 2.5 h in aerial atmosphere. It was observed that the colour of the iron(III)-Schiff base complexes became intensified upon addition of TBHP. Upon addition of substrate to the reaction mixtures, solutions' colour started to fade and after completion of reactions, intensity of the solutions' colour almost turned back similar to the original intensity. This visual observation recommends the regeneration of active iron(III) catalysts in solution. The progress of the reaction was monitored by TLC. The organic products were extracted with diethyl ether, dried with Na_2SO_4 and filtered. After usual work up and chromatographic purification, the epoxide products were identified by ^1H NMR spectroscopy (Fig. S6).

Supplementary data

FT-IR, UV-Vis spectra, ESI-MS spectrometry measurements, ^1H NMR spectra, computational details are given in supporting information.

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Sahu *et al.*: Synthesis, spectroscopic characterization with computational modeling *etc.*

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